

Application Guidelines to improve visual comfort

EMRP-ENG05-3.2.2

Version 2.0

12/06/2013 – for update tracking

(officialy 30th April 2013)

Giuseppe Rossi
INRIM

Paola Iacomussi
INRIM

Michela Radis
INRIM

Dominique Renoux
LNE

Jordi Nonne
LNE

Gabriele Piccablotto
CCR

A report of the EMRP Joint Research Project

Metrology for Solid State Lighting

www.m4ssl.npl.co.uk

Title	:	Application guidelines to improve visual comfort
Reference	:	EMRP-ENG05-3.2.2
Version	:	2.0
Date	:	30-05-2013
Dissemination level	:	PUBLIC
Author(s)	:	Giuseppe Rossi, Paola Iacomussi, Michela Radis INRIM Dominique Renoux, Jordi Nonne LNE Gabriele Piccablotto CCR
Keywords	:	Luminaire characterization, visual comfort, overhead glare
Abstract	:	The report describes guidelines for the improvement of visual comfort of lighting environments using SSL, providing easy to use suggestion for designers..
Contact	:	http://www.m4ssl.npl.co.uk/contact

About the EMRP

The European Metrology Research Programme (EMRP) is a metrology-focused European programme of coordinated R&D that facilitates closer integration of national research programmes. The EMRP is jointly supported by the European Commission and the participating countries within the European Association of National Metrology Institutes (EURAMET e.V.). The EMRP will ensure collaboration between National Measurement Institutes, reducing duplication and increasing impact. The overall goal of the EMRP is to accelerate innovation and competitiveness in Europe whilst continuing to provide essential support to underpin the quality of our lives. See <http://www.emrponline.eu> for more information.

About the EMRP JRP “Metrology for Solid State Lighting”

In the EMRP Joint Research Project (JRP) “Metrology for Solid State Lighting”, the following partners cooperate to create a European infrastructure for the traceable measurement of solid state lighting: VSL (Coordinator), Aalto, CMI, CSIC, EJP, INRIM, IPQ, LNE, MKEH, NPL, PTB, SMU, SP, Trescal, CCR, TU Ilmenau and Université Paul Sabatier. See <http://www.m4ssl.npl.co.uk/> for more information.

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union on the basis of Decision No 912/2009/EC.

SUMMARY

This report considers the results of subjective experiments of Deliverable D3.2.1 “Report on measurement procedure of visual comfort” and D3.2.3 “Report on measurement conditions and parameters to correctly evaluate glare of SSL luminaries” and other experiment about the evaluation of visual comfort for specific lighting set up. From the above results a ranking of the relevant parameters for assuring visual comfort, with SSL lighting, is provided. About comfort it is necessary to note that a robust definition of visual comfort doesn't exist. The most widely accepted approach is that comfort is not discomfort, because it is easier to provide quantitative and qualitative evaluation of discomfort parameters. For this reason in several lighting set up the glare perception (UGR value) plays a relevant role, but some cases where glare is well tolerated (and underestimated by subjects) exist. The synoptic table provided of relevant parameter for visual comfort is a first step in order to define the most relevant quality aspect to take care in SSL lighting.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1 INTRODUCTION	3
2 VISUAL COMFORT RELEVANT PARAMETERS	4
2.3. Available suggestions for visual comfort.....	5
2.3.1. <i>Indoor lighting</i>	5
2.3.2. <i>Outdoor lighting</i>	5
3 CONTRIBUTIONS FOR IMPROVING VISUAL COMFORT WITH SSL	7
3.1 General aspects.....	7
3.2 Glare	7
2.4. Synoptic table	8
4 CONCLUSIONS	1
5 REFERENCES	2

LIST OF FIGURES

LIST OF SYMBOLS

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

CCT	Correlated Colour Temperature
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CIE	Commission Internationale de l'Eclairage
EMRP	European Metrology Research Programme
IESNA	Illuminating Engineering Society of North America
JRP	Joint Research Project
LED	Ligth-emitting Diode
NMI	National Metrology Institute
q_r	Installation luminance factor
SSL	Solid State Lighting
STV	Small Target Visibility
TI	Threshold Increment
UGR	Unified Glare Rating
ULOR	Upward Light Output Ratio
UNI	Ente Nazionale Italiano di Unificazione (Italian Standard Organization)
VCP	Visual Comfort Probability

1 INTRODUCTION

With the recent introduction of SSL, following the deployment of fluorescent compact sources and the now old linear fluorescents sources, and with the increasing number of lighting manufacturers, the diversity of lighting has considerably grown whereas the basic practices and knowledge related to lighting quality has not evolved. SSL also presents more flexibility than traditional lighting varying light distribution and spectral content. These effects, properly managed, have the potential to improve visual task performance, visual comfort and safety but also present new sources of discomfort and hazard. The studies conducted in this JRP, reported in the deliverable D.3.2.1[1], were driven to develop our knowledge on perceived visual comfort of lighting environments through subjective experiments and to derive psychophysical parameters and models of visual comfort. This second deliverable on visual comfort, exploits the outcomes of the above-mentioned studies and other available researches and provides guidance and easy to apply suggestions to improve visual comfort for relevant applications with SSL sources.

2 VISUAL COMFORT RELEVANT PARAMETERS

As stated in D.3.2.1 [1] a widely accepted definition of visual comfort doesn't exist. One of the mostly used approach to visual comfort is based on what comfort isn't: providing indications on what is better to avoid in order to not have possible users annoyance.

CIE, standards on lighting environments and available research specify/recognize the following parameters as relevant for visual comfort:

- Glare (overhead, from surfaces);
- Veiling reflections;
- Illuminance levels (work plane, surrounding,..);
- Luminance ratios;
- Colour rendering index – CRI;
- Correlated Colour Temperature – CCT (K);
- Flicker

For the visual comfort appraisal other research also consider:

- Space and room appearance;
- Surfaces brightness;
- Light distribution;
- Appearance of the light and of the luminaire.

In SSL lighting the most relevant parameters, that are significantly different from diffuse fluorescent lighting on which the available guidance are based, are listed hereafter:

- Spectral lighting distribution;
- Light source size;
- Luminaire appearance.

These parameters can lead to conspicuous differences on the visual comfort perception and have been investigated in WP3 with different experiments. This report summarizes the available results and provides indications about visual comfort.

2.3. Available suggestions for visual comfort

2.3.1. Indoor lighting

Indoor work places context

European standard EN 12464-01 [2], specifies requirements for enabling people to efficiently and accurately perform visual tasks, assuring visual comfort, for different categories of working place, included public areas, shops etc... The standard recognizes the need of not only quantitative requirements – quantity of light - but also qualitative requirements related to the quality of light and measured through glare indices, luminance distributions, colour rendering indices, and correlated colour temperature, etc... Usually quantitative values are based on the approach of task performance specifying the correct value's ranges assuring the correct implementation of tasks. This task-related approach of visual comfort is only based on good practice rules avoiding too high or too low luminance and/or contrast levels, glare and flickering.

Generally, it is suggested to keep the value of the uniformity of the illuminance greater than 0.40 in the surrounding area and greater than 0.10 in the background area, specific values for reference area – or task area - are given in the detailed columns of application tables of the standard. No quantitative indications are specified for luminance uniformities, but qualitative suggestions are given for luminance distributions. Recommended reflectance of surfaces, illuminance values and uniformities are provided in order to meet appropriate luminance distribution. Available guidelines and quantitative/qualitative parameters are derived from studies conducted with diffuse fluorescent lighting, several studies investigated if whether these guidelines and parameters are transferable to LED lighting. Several research experiments have been performed with LED lighting but as no standard setup have been defined, and due to the diversity of characteristics of the tested LED sources and luminaire no clear indication can be extrapolated and in many cases the results of research are inconclusive.

Domestic lighting context

Domestic lighting applications are not covered by any standard or guideline for visual comfort. The purpose of the lighting for such places is not in general to facilitate a visual task, or increase the efficiency of a visual task, but to create an atmosphere, e.g. relaxing or appealing, with or without aesthetical effects revealing attractively the environment. The concern for with discomfort parameters, as glare and flicker, is common to any lighting environment, with possible difference in their threshold accounting for the specific condition of exposure with regards to the environment. The attributes to consider could be different or identical than those of [2], but the same parameter may be requires very different values to achieve different effects as it arrives for the uniformity of illuminance: higher values recommended in work spaces, and lower values in convivial spaces.

2.3.2. Outdoor lighting

In outdoor lighting, i.e. outdoor work places, road lighting and city beautification, the requirements are very different. In the first two applications the most important characteristic of a lighting system is its ability to

assure safety, while the third application has purely aesthetic and decorative purpose, no standard is available because is essentially managed at town level using indications provided by relevant CIE document about it [3] considering indications about lighting pollution (that nothing has to do with comfort) and obstrusive lighting (that can involve discomfort inside houses).

Outdoor work places context

About outdoor working places standard EN 12464-02 [3] CIE 1993, CIE 94:1993 Guide for Floodlighting, Vienna: CIE

[4] keep the same approach of standard part 1 [2]: quantitative and qualitative requirements are related both to the quantity of light able to assure the safety and task performance and quality of light suggesting parameters to care of like glare, obstrusive light, glare, veiling reflection...

EN standard [4] suggests to provide well balance luminance ratio, avoiding veiling reflection, reflection glare, flickering and stroboscopic effects. The obstrusive light is tolerated but depending on the environmental zone. Recommended illuminance values, uniformities, color rendering are provided in order to assure the satisfaction of the visual task requirements, visual comfort is a secondary parameter not considered in details. More information about qualitative parameters in outdoor lighting standard can be found in [6].

Road lighting context

In road lighting the first scope of lighting is to assure safety of all road users: so the most important thing is to assure the perception of obstacles (or pedestrian) and the overcome of visual threshold for the visual task. Comfort is also considered but as secondary aspect. Comfort is taken in account through suggestions about: colour appearance and colour rendering of the light, mounting height of the luminaire, lit appearance of the luminaire and of the complete installation, optical guidance by direct light from the luminaire, disability glare (threshold increment), reduction of light levels in periods and minimizing light emitted in directions where it is neither necessary nor desirable (the so called obstrusive light, light seen at a distance across open country, intruding into properties and lighting pollution). Only for few of these parameters also some quantitative data are provided, in particular only for disability glare and obstrusive light indication about maximum allowed TI (between 10 and 15) and luminous intensity at 3 different angles of elevation. But even if the standard doesn't refer to illuminance and luminance uniformity as comfort parameters, it is clear that higher uniformities do not improve only safety but also comfort. About colour rendering no special requirement are declared, but the weak indication given on standard suggestions about comfort is secondary to energy saving or installation arrangements. More information about qualitative parameters in road lighting standard can be found in [6].

3 CONTRIBUTIONS FOR IMPROVING VISUAL COMFORT WITH SSL

3.1 General aspects

Today SSL products are mainly based on single or array of small point sources, LED chips or dies, which present high-brightness and specific spectra, the most common type being a combination of a broad yellow peak – from phosphor conversion – and a narrow blue peak - from the emission of the exciting LED. The LED source output presents also a very short response time and depending on the electronic can present important flicker or modulation. Luminaires are featured with lenses, diffusers, and reflectors for beam shaping of the radiated light from the LED point sources. The size and the luminance levels can vary in size from few mm to several tens of mm and in luminance from 10^5 cd/m² to 10^8 cd/m². Then these specific properties of SSL could create specific effects on visual comfort of lighting installation. The published studies and the work done for that project bring some information that can be considered for related guidelines and supporting metrics of visual comfort.

3.2 Glare

Glare is one of the most important parameter to consider, some general statements can be drawn from literature review and work performed at LNE and INRIM, specific information are also in [7].

The research about the evaluation of glare effect due to SSL lighting is very large: review of performed experiments demonstrates that available metrics for discomfort glare are still applicable if the SSL sources or luminaires do not significantly differ, in term of intensity and luminance distribution, from fluorescent lighting (so with LED not clearly visible or with some kind of diffuser). Existing criteria seems not to be applicable for non-uniform sources with LED clearly visible, but a lot of available researches are still inconclusive.

An experiment conducted by INRIM showed that

- the effect of glare is practically independent for the LED source and incandescent lamp, but a lower adaptation luminances (9 cd m²) the LED ensure better performance for negative contrast.
- the effect of glare is practically independent from the glare source type at higher adaptation luminances (22 cd m²) while at lower adaptation luminances LED (9 cd m²) LED sources give better performances then incandescent lamps.

So this experiment confirmed that SSL equipped with diffuser do not differ from traditional lighting sources.

Another experiment of INRIM showed that the pupil size is affected by the luminance and spectrum distribution of the source. Experiment results highlight a significant influence of the source spectral distribution and observed target on pupil size: at given luminance, the LED source always gives a smaller pupil diameter, if compared to the other two tested sources (incandescent and metal halide lamps).

Two experiments conducted at LNE showed that the actual formula of UGR is well correlated with subjective rating in a simple test experiment, lamps in uniform background, and in a complex environment in a living room with wall and ceiling luminaires.

The model for visual comfort set up in [1] gives to glare the maximum weight, so it is clear that glare is the most effective parameter in judging the comfort of a lighting installation.

Other researches indicate that even a relevant amount of glare can be tolerated, the lighting set up with the smaller amount of glare cannot be the best comfortable solution by subjects. In a research conducted on show cases [8] three different lighting set up (lighting from above, below and side), two different SSL CCT (warm and cold), with the same illuminance on the target (300 lx), were analysed. The scenes were objectively characterized for maximum luminance, target luminance (average), background average luminance, target uniformity (minimum/average), UGR and uniformity target-background (average).

The solution with the highest score of comfort and preference, by the 20 subjects attending the experiment, was that one with the highest score of target and background uniformities, target-background contrast and averaged background luminance. The luminance of the target was relevant too because the chosen set up provide the highest target mean luminance (at the same illuminance on the exposition plane). While the glare was not relevant: the UGR was calculated using both Guth and Kim & Kim indexes and provided a values between 17 to 30. For the chosen set up the subjective evaluation of glare was not consistent with the provided calculation (value of 26, with a remarkable subjective 60% underestimation), while for all the other set up the subjective evaluation was in good accordance.

Even if this specific test was conducted for show cases it is possible to extrapolate that the glare should not be the main parameters to evaluate visual comfort; for task related lighting target visibility and uniformities play a more relevant role than the glare index.

3.3 Synoptic table

From [1], [8] [9] it is possible to define a ranking of the parameters considered in the model explained in [1] about visual comfort in SSL lighting. The ranking is show in Table 1.

It is to keep in mind that the ranking provided refers to the set up considered in the experiments from which the parameters was tested, it is possible that for different set up (i.e. lighting levels, luminaires, CRI etc...) the weight values were not correct, but it should be valid the ranking order in terms of relevance of the parameters.

Available literature, like [9] did not provide a ranking of parameter for assuring visual comfort, the main parameters for indoor lighting are described in [10]. IESNA document [11] provides a ranking of parameter for assuring a good lighting quality in indoor lighting valid for traditional lighting (i.e. fluorescent lamps), for some cases a good accordance is shown.

Table 1 Ranking of relevant parameter of visual comfort model for SSL lighting from [1]

Task related lighting		Living room lighting		Compartment lighting		Office lighting	
Parameter ref. Fig. 26 of [1]	Weight	Parameter ref. Fig. 26 of [1]	Weight	Parameter ref. Fig. 26 of [1]	Weight	Parameter ref. Fig. 26 of [1]	Weight
Light distribution (uniformity on target)	100	Glare (low UGR value)	100	Glare (low UGR value)	100	Glare (low UGR value)	100
Contrast object/background	100	Contrast object / background	27	Lighting levels	33	Light distribution (uniformities)	17
Background uniformity	100	Luminaire appearance	27	Contrast object / background	33	Contrast object / background	12
Target averaged luminance	80	Lighting levels	18	CCT effects	11	CCT effects	12
Lighting levels	75	CCT effects	9	Colour rendering	6	Lighting levels	6
Luminaire appearance	50	Colour rendering	5	Light distribution (uniformities)	not relevant	Mixing effects of CCT in the visual field	6
Glare (low UGR value)	50	Mixing effects of CCT in the visual field	not relevant	Luminaire appearance	not relevant	Colour rendering	3
CCT effects	not considered	Light distribution (uniformities)	not relevant	Mixing effects of CCT in the visual field	not relevant	Luminaire appearance	not relevant
Colour rendering	not considered	Target averaged luminance	not considered	Target averaged luminance	not considered	Target averaged luminance	not considered
Mixing effects of CCT in the visual field	not considered	Background uniformity	not considered	Background uniformity	not considered	Background uniformity	not considered

4 CONCLUSIONS

From the results of different subjective experiments and from the visual comfort model of [1] it is possible to say:

- available metrics for discomfort glare are still applicable if the SSL sources or luminaires do not significantly differ, in term of intensity and luminance distribution, from fluorescent light, so in order to improve and assure better performance and reliability on the results, it is better to equip SSL lighting with diffuser or to design set up able to hide from the direct view the SSL;
- for special kind of lighting set up, like “task related lighting” like to highlights objects in showcases, the direct vision of SSL is well tolerated and the glare doesn’t play a relevant role in discomfort, but only if the uniformities on background and target are high as well as the contrast between object and background;
- for the other typical lighting set up like living room, compartment and office lighting, avoiding glare is the most relevant parameter to fulfill in order to increase visual comfort;
- the UGR values weight (for lower values) has the highest weight in comparison to all other parameters involved in the visual comfort evaluation (three times more for living room and compartement lighting, while for office lighting is quite six times more important);
- flickering effects were not considered in this study.

5 REFERENCES

- [1] D.3.2.1 – ENG05 deliverable report “Report on measurement procedure of visual comfort”
- [2] EN 12464-01:2011 Lighting of work place – Indoor work places
- [3] CIE 1993, CIE 94:1993 Guide for Floodlighting, Vienna: CIE
- [4] EN 12464-02:2008 Lighting of work place – Outdoor work places
- [5] EN 13201-02:2004 Road Lighting – Performance requirements
- [6] D.4.5.1 – ENG05 deliverable report “Report on aspects of outdoor lighting”
- [7] D.3.2.3 – ENG05 deliverable report “Report on measurement conditions and parameters to correctly evaluate glare of SSL luminaries”
- [8] Gabriele Piccablotto “Solid State lighting system for applications in museum”, PhD thesis
- [9] CIE (201x) CIE XXX:201x Review of lighting quality measures for interior lighting with LED lighting systems. (to date in state of Committee Draft)
- [10] D.4.4.1 – ENG05 deliverable report “Report considering general aspect in indoor lighting”
- [11] IESNA 2000, *IESNA Lighting Design Guide in The IESNA lighting handbook. Reference & application*. 9th edition. New York: Mark S. Rea